

Deliverable D2.2 Report on the ready-to-use training materials for usage and rolling-out in Task 2.3

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Contribution toward project objectives	3
3. Introduction	4
4. Description of work accomplished	5
4.1 Development of training Materials	5
4.2 Activities related to TeSS and RDMkit	6
TeSS	6
RDMkit	6
5. Results	6
5.1 Statistics	6
5.2 Training materials for the four WP2 priority topics	7
5.2.1 Data Management Plan (DMP)	7
5.2.2 FAIR	8
5.2.3 General DM/DS	8
5.2.4 Reproducibility	9
5.3 Training activities in collaboration with WP5 (Demonstrators)	9
5.4 Train the trainer	10
5.4.1 “Regular” TtT	10
5.4.2. TtT FAIR Implementation	10
5.5 FEGA	11
5.6 CONVERGE Uplift: CoP and ELITMa	11
5.6.1 CoP	11
5.6.2 ELITMa	12
5.7 Learning Paths	13
5.8 Activities related to TeSS and RDMkit	14
5.8.1 TeSS & RDMkit hackathons related to training materials and events	14
5.8.2 Controlled vocabularies	14
5.8.3 RDMkit: Links to TeSS and Your Role Pages	15
5.9 Collaboration with ELIXIR Training Platform	15
6. Conclusions	16
7. Impact	17
8. Next Steps	17

1. Executive Summary

Research data Management (RDM, also used interchangeably with Data Management/Data Stewardship, abbreviated as DM/DS) is central to the implementation of the FAIR (Findable Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Open Science principles. Recognising the importance of RDM, the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project was launched in 2020 and included a work package on Training & Capacity Building in Data Stewardship, in which 21 Nodes participated. The aim of WP2 is to build a comprehensive, interconnected and sustainable RDM Training Portfolio across all Nodes, and to increase the DM/DS training expertise and capacity in ELIXIR Nodes. This is accomplished by unlocking the expertise in the ELIXIR Nodes, and building on and aligning with their national needs and strategies towards RDM Training.

In the project period (Feb 2020 - June 2023) training materials were developed, belonging to 133 training events, which were organised by 18 Nodes and served 4226 participants. In this deliverable an overview is presented of the developed training materials and other supporting training-related activities during the project period.

The project started with a training gap analysis (D2.1), with the aim to understand the demand of topics that are needed for development across the Nodes. This yielded four priority topics: Data Management Plans (DMPs), FAIR, Reproducibility and General DM/DS. Nodes contributed to the development of materials for the topic(s) of their choice and need. In addition training-related activities were performed in collaboration with WP5 (Demonstrators), WP3 (related to RDMkit) and the ELIXIR Training Platform (related to TeSS, Learning Paths and Train-the-Trainer). Finally, training-related activities were undertaken in the two WP2 Uplift projects: CoP (Community of Practice) and ELITMa (ELIXIR Training in Management). With WP1, there was a strong collaboration with the WP1 data managers network to strengthen implementation of training efforts in the Nodes and with the dedicated WP1 training group.

To support all these activities groundwork has been done related to identifying common vocabularies to annotate the training products properly, to register and annotate WP2 outcomes in TeSS, to establish training links between TeSS and RDMkit, and to establish the Your Role pages in RDMkit, based on the ELIXIR/NPOS data stewardship competency framework.

Going forward the outputs of CONVERGE WP2 will be embedded and sustained in the ELIXIR Training Platform, coordinated by the ELIXIR RDM Trainer Network, which is an integral part of the new ELIXIR RDM Community.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	Yes
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	Yes
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available	No

according to international standards.	
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

Considering the clear need for the increase in and dissemination of Data Management and Data stewardship (DM/DS) know-how, practices and resources and the demand for DM/DS training material and courses, for researchers, trainers and DM/DS professionals, the aim of WP2 is to build a comprehensive, interconnected and sustainable DM/DS Training Portfolio across all Nodes, and to increase the DM/DS training expertise and capacity in ELIXIR Nodes.

In this deliverable work is described that relates to all three objectives of WP2:

O2.1: Build a comprehensive, interconnected and sustainable ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management across all Nodes

O2.2: Connect the activities in the ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management sustainably to the national roadmaps of the Nodes

O2.3: Establish high level of Data Management and Data Stewardship knowledge and expertise across ELIXIR Nodes

The resulting ELIXIR DM/DS Course portfolio includes training courses and training materials for data managers, researchers and trainers, which will be findable in the ELIXIR Training Portal TeSS and reusable for future use. Twenty-one ELIXIR Nodes participate in WP2, who all brought in their expertise to build this portfolio. They did this also in line with their national training agenda and national training needs. Together with experts from the other Work Packages (WP1 - in particular the WP1 data managers network & the WP1 training group - , WP3, WP5, WP6, WP7/9), and in close collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform a large portfolio of training materials has been developed and is described here. These collaborations will continue beyond the end of ELIXIR-CONVERGE in the recently created ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community, of which the RDM Trainer Network, established in WP2, is an integral part. This community will bring together the expertise, experience, people, tools and knowledge in DM/DS, gathered together in this project, and thus ensure the work developed in ELIXIR-CONVERGE will continue.

4. Description of work accomplished

The work that has been accomplished and will be described here consists of:

1. Development of training materials
2. Activities related to TeSS and RDMkit

4.1 Development of training Materials

In the CONVERGE project the following training-related materials have been developed in WP2 and will be described in detail in Section 5:

- As described in [D2.1](#)¹ a gap analysis was performed by the WP2 members and Nodes and resulted in a list of 14 topics. During the General Assembly 2021 the WP2 members prioritised four topics (DMP, FAIR, general DM/DS and Reproducibility) for which specific WP2 material generating hackathons have been organised.
- In addition, all WP2 Nodes have been building training materials that were needed in their national context.
- In collaboration with WP5 (Demonstrators) dedicated training & capacity building activities have been undertaken.
- In the CONVERGE Uplift two projects were granted (CoP and ELITMa) and for both materials have been built.
- Train-the-trainer materials related to DM/DS
- Learning Paths for DM/DS have been developed during Biohackathon2022, in a collaboration between the ELIXIR Training Platform and WP2.

¹https://zenodo.org/record/4892863#_YN2mdpNKi0o

- First steps have been taken for training activities related to FEGA

Note: Here we will describe training materials for courses and workshops. Dissemination activities (presentations, webinars etc.) by WP2 are described in the companion [Deliverable 2.5](#)² and are also described in the [ELIXIR-CONVERGE dissemination spreadsheet](#)³. As also described in D2.5, distinguishing between training and dissemination activities can sometimes be challenging, as overlaps or blurred boundaries between both may exist. In the context of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, we defined training as any event that enables participants to learn something new or improve their skills.

4.2 Activities related to TeSS and RDMkit

TeSS

It is the ultimate goal to have all WP2 materials properly annotated and easily findable in [TeSS](#)⁴, the ELIXIR Training Portal. To make this happen, work has been undertaken related to defining which controlled vocabulary/vocabularies would be useful for this purpose. Collaboration has been sought with EDAM and with terms4fairskills. Ultimately, it was decided to formulate a WP2 endorsed tag list that WP2 members could use. This was needed because EDAM did not yet contain sufficient DM/DS terms and terms4fairskills was not mature enough yet and also was not yet implemented in TeSS.

RDMkit

The aim is to establish appropriate links from the RDMkit developed in WP3 to relevant training events and materials in TeSS, so visitors from the RDMkit pages can be routed very easily to training materials that are useful for them. A subgroup of WP2 members has worked closely with the RDMkit team to make this happen.

Another activity related to the RDMkit are the Your role pages, where WP2 members have played an important role. The roles that are mentioned in the Your role pages emerge from the data stewardship competency framework that was developed in a collaboration of ELIXIR/WP2 and the Dutch Open Science Programme (NPOS).

5. Results

5.1 Statistics

²<https://zenodo.org/record/8168647>

³https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OGNHLElusi99BpT63NGeh_qRY9cMpKUBmVEGjollLumO/edit#gid=1539160517

⁴<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

The [WP2 Inventory spreadsheet](#)⁵ gives all the training events (including their materials) that have been organised by WP2 members during the CONVERGE project period:

133 Events, 18 Nodes, 4226 participants (Feb 2020 - June 2023)

5.2 Training materials for the four WP2 priority topics

After the General Assembly 2021, where the 4 priority topics (DMP, DM/DS, Reproducibility, FAIR (incl metadata)) were chosen, a process was started to identify champions for each of the 4 topics, who then made a proposal for their approach. After this, an open invitation was done to WP2 members and other interested individuals (inside and outside ELIXIR) and the work started on the four topics. On March 24, 2022, a kick-off meeting for material generation hackathons was hosted by ELIXIR-DE. After the kickoff the 4 groups have followed their own plan of approach and timeline in the generation of their materials and this is described in the paragraphs below.

5.2.1 Data Management Plan (DMP)

The aim of this training project was to create new and standardised training materials for DMP training courses (face-to-face and online formats). ELIXIR-DE took the lead and organised five hackathon sessions in 2022 (29 March / 1 April / 8 April / 10 May / 3 June) to produce new DMP training materials. A total of 20 participants from 9 different nodes were involved in these sessions (DE, DK, LU, ES, BE, SI, UK, CH, SE). The group created content for a beginner audience, using practical examples and interactive sessions. These sessions allowed to share best practices for DMPs in a structured and accessible way, enabling researchers to use different tools and templates for their DMPs.

Subsequently, in an internal session (24 August 2022) the resulting material was reviewed. The final material was used in 3 different face-to-face training courses ([GCB 2022](#), [ECCB 2022](#), [de.NBI Spring](#)

⁵<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-gzbJZOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit#gid=857055246>

[School 2023](#)⁶) and an online webinar (GHGA webinar). Based on the feedback and experiences gathered from these training courses, the material was further refined and adapted to the needs of the participants.

In addition, a hackathon was organised in 2023 with 8 participants to update the DMP training material. Another training course using the material is planned for September 2023. Finally, it is planned to upload the final material to Zenodo.

5.2.2 FAIR

Since June 2022, in ELIXIR-CONVERGE context, 3 hackathons-style events (June 29, September 12, december 14) have been organised with the (beyond life sciences) community to develop FAIR lesson plans, co-led by ELIXIR-Netherlands and ELIXIR-Sweden. Community-led, open lesson plans originate from the [2021 FAIRsFAIR training handbook](#)⁷, addressing competencies, training designs and 16 lesson plans. Although initiated in the context of ELIXIR, the hackathons are open to participants outside ELIXIR, making it a cross-domain effort along the lines of the original FAIRsFAIR handbook.

The events targeted people with an interest in research data management in the life sciences (trainers, data stewards, researchers, etc.) and offered the opportunity to jointly create additional lesson plans to help research organisations advance their data stewards' and researchers' FAIR skills (how do you go/do FAIR). These lesson plans include links to existing materials (e.g. knowledge clips, guidelines, etc.) that organisations may use in their training programmes, but also identify gaps and make suggestions for additional material to be developed.

Although lesson plans aren't ready-to-go courses yet, they offer the framework and are the basis for FAIR training. A community-led exercise helped to harmonise FAIR training efforts and create a basis for the implementation of FAIR data in local organisations: what do researchers, data stewards, other data experts have to be skilled in to apply FAIR in projects and to datasets?

Using an adapted lesson plan template based on the FAIRsFAIR handbook and building upon its existing lessons, an adapted curriculum of seven units was created: FAIR generics, Findable data, Accessible data, Interoperable data, Reusable data, FAIR software, and Data repositories. In total, over 70 participants from 13 Nodes (NL, DE, NO, FR, UK, BE, EBI-EMBL, LU, SE, FI, AT, EE, ES) participated. The lesson plans are [published](#)⁸ in 2023 via the ELIXIR Training GitHub. ELIXIR Nodes are encouraged to use the lesson plans in their teaching on FAIR.

Work will be continued during [BioHackathon 2023](#)⁹, aimed to gain insight into existing materials for researchers and data stewards focused on FAIR data management, and adding relevant elements from those materials to existing lesson plans. Furthermore, we plan to create content for new lesson plans. The further work on the lesson plans will also be consolidated in the Implementation Study of the ELIXIR RDM Community, which is expected to start early 2024.

⁶<https://docs.denbi.de/s/2ommENybEgPEC4m?dir=undefined&openfile=98096>

⁷<https://fairsfair.gitbook.io/fair-teaching-handbook/>

⁸<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-Converge/>

⁹<https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2023/tree/main/11>

5.2.3 General DM/DS

For the topic of general DM/DS ELIXIR-SE, ELIXIR-PT and ELIXIR-SI took the lead and worked together with ELIXIR Sweden in the preparation of a curriculum to onboard data stewards at different levels: beginner and with experiences. Several meetings took place starting June 2022 and after a few hackathons in May 2023 the final curriculum was constructed and made ready for review and being made available at the GitHub for further use. Going forward the plan is to actually take advantage of the constructed curriculum to generate training materials and resource collections to offer courses and resources that allow life science organisations to support the onboarding of new data stewards. These resources will continuously update the created curriculum and be integrated into learning paths for on boarding data stewards for life sciences.

A [repository with the outcomes of this task](#) was created in GitHub and will continue to be updated.

5.2.4 Reproducibility

The Code Reproducibility Training project is co-led by ELIXIR-UK and ELIXIR-Norway. The aim of the project is to create training materials using the newly launched [ELIXIR Training Lesson template](#)¹⁰, to help learners acquire the core skills required to develop sustainable and reproducible code. We do so by creating educational content and training targeted for an audience with non-computing backgrounds, using hands-on examples that are developed further in each subsequent lesson creating a learning path for users to follow. This enables us to share best coding practices in a structured and accessible way, allowing learners to utilise tools and practices that were previously limited to the computational-savvy.

Six topics were identified for development within the reproducibility theme: Literate Programming, Version Control, Documentation, Testing, Containers, Continuous Integration/Deployment. Lessons on these six topics are developed in two sub-tracks; one for R and one for Python. Discussions with different data Reproducibility-focused organisations such as the Software Sustainability Institute, [UK Reproducibility Network](#)¹¹ (UKRN) and [Norway's Reproducibility Network](#)¹² (NorRN) took place to identify possible collaborations and also to use the networks to recruit developers/maintainers of these lessons. This in fact resulted in 50+ registrations (participants coming from DE, BE, SE, UK, NO, LU, FR, EST, SI, South Africa, Australia, Cameroon) after the recruitment for lessons development was advertised in December 2022.

The development of these training materials is still ongoing and updates will be posted in the [CodeReproducibility website](#)¹³ that is currently under development. The project is in discussions with the ELIXIR Hub to look into the possibility of continuing its effort via other programmes, such as the ELIXIR Tools platform and other relevant projects as discussed in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Long-Term Sustainability meeting 2023 in Dublin.

¹⁰<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-LessonTemplate-MkDocs/>

¹¹<https://www.ukrn.org/>

¹²<https://www.norrn.no/>

¹³<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/CodeReproducibility/index>

5.3 Training activities in collaboration with WP5 (Demonstrators)

One of the objectives of WP5 was to identify the needs in terms of capacity building, in the context of the 6 use cases, and to develop strategy(ies) in collaboration with WP2 to address these needs. This was achieved in three steps:

- Create an inventory of training resources available in the context of the use cases
- Send an online survey followed by a series of F2F meetings with each use case to collect their training needs
- Test the development of learning paths as a method to develop a structured overview of training needs in relation to a use case, in collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform.

The approach implemented by the ELIXIR Training Platform for organising the development of training resources was highly beneficial in effectively identifying training requirements and promoting capacity building within specific use cases. By clearly defining training objectives and outlining the learning path necessary to achieve these objectives, the method enabled a detailed breakdown of the required modules. Consequently, existing training resources could be mapped onto these modules, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of any existing gaps. This methodology was successfully employed in three demonstration cases: Plant, Marine metagenomics, and Human Genome data contexts.

WP2 and WP5 have been collaborating closely and the work has been described in detail in [D5.3 Report on the dedicated training and capacity building activities](#)¹⁴.

5.4 Train the trainer

Since there is a need to increase the number of people in the Nodes who have RDM training expertise, WP2 set out to establish train-the-trainer activities. A survey for the trainers of DM/DS has been prepared and sent out in December 2021 to assess the pedagogical challenges and needs faced by trainers who teach in data management and data stewardship courses, as well as their profiles. The target audience of this survey was instructors and future instructors in data management and data stewardship of short or long courses, in education or training, mainly (but not limited to) in life or health sciences. The survey was answered by 52 individuals from across the globe.

5.4.1 “Regular” TtT

Two Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events were conducted, following the successful format of the regular ELIXIR-GOBLET [TtT of the ELIXIR Training Platform](#)¹⁵ (TrP). These events, organised by ELIXIR-UK from 19th to 22nd October 2021 and by ELIXIR-ES from 23rd to 26th November 2021, included insightful discussions on the challenges associated with teaching Data Management/Data Stewardship (DM/DS).

¹⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/7858328#.ZEZXWQzML0o>

¹⁵<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training/train-the-trainer>

One key takeaway from these discussions and the survey was that the pedagogical challenges in teaching DM/DS topics are minimal, as the content is relatively straightforward. However, the real obstacles lie in motivating researchers to actually participate in DM/DS courses and overcoming their lack of enthusiasm or resistance towards investing time in understanding how to make data FAIR.

Based on the conclusions drawn from these discussions, an important project was initiated: the creation of a video aimed at raising awareness about the crucial need for effective data management. This initiative, detailed in the accompanying [deliverable D2.5](#)¹⁶, aims to address the challenge of motivating researchers and convincing them of the significance and necessity of DM/DS courses.

The other conclusion from the survey and discussions was the need to create TtT modules in data management topics, which aligned with the needs identified (see above) within the WP2 members.

5.4.2. TtT FAIR Implementation

Led by ELIXIR-NL and with collaboration of UK, PT, SE and NO, in 2022 work started on a specific TtT on FAIR Implementation, aimed at facilitating trainers in their organisation to make data FAIR. Aim was to build on existing efforts, more specifically the didactical content of the regular TtT combined with FAIR specific content. However, since a structured ELIXIR FAIR curriculum was lacking at the start of the activity, the decision was to switch focus to creating FAIR lesson plans first (see section 5.2.2), for which the first content is now published. This offers an excellent opportunity to embed and continue the work on the TtT on FAIR Implementation, in the context of the ELIXIR RDM Community.

5.5 FEAGA

WP2 aims to build an ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management (DM) across all Nodes and WP7 focuses on building resources to support the Federated EGA for transnational access of data. The main focus of WP7 at the moment is to provide motivational information and materials for national FEAGA users. There have been several coordinated activities between WP2 and WP7 to support training and capacity building activities in WP7. Two examples are highlighted here:

- ELIXIR-FI published (spring 2023) a [tutorial video series](#)¹⁷ about Federated EGA (metadata and phenotypic metadata & covid-19 as an example) and a [FEAGA User Guide](#)¹⁸

¹⁶<https://zenodo.org/record/8168647>

¹⁷https://video.csc.fi/playlist/dedicated/0_ip0b3jibh/0_tlk289fi

¹⁸<https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/federatedega/>

- Presentation and guided discussion on training opportunities during the “Federated EGA Onboarding Website, Maturity Model, and Training Thon Event” that took place on the 15-16 May, 2023 at the EMBL-EBI ([agenda](#)¹⁹ and [slides](#)²⁰). Possible actions in the future for the Federated EGA and the ELIXIR Federated Human Data community would be to landscape Federated EGA nodes and staff on their training needs, existing materials and identify gaps, compile existing materials in a TeSS collection (e.g. including onboarding website, EGA training), and cross-work with the ELIXIR Federated Human Data community and the ELIXIR Training Platform following a co-production model to develop and execute training and capacity building.
- Presentation of training opportunities and synergies with the ELIXIR Federated Human Data community bimonthly call on the 27, June, 2023 ([slides](#)²¹) to stimulate community discussions on training aspects, increase the adoption and usage of the ELIXIR Training Platform services and consider the co-production model on their future training developments and activities.

5.6 CONVERGE Uplift: CoP and ELITMa

In 2022 two CONVERGE uplift projects started in WP2, [CoP](#)²² (Community of Practice) and [ELITMa](#)²³ (ELIXIR Training in Management). Both have their own project description and deliverables but a short summary of both is given here.

5.6.1 CoP

In March 2022, the Community of Practice (CoP) in training for Data Management and Data Stewardship (DM/DS) was launched as part of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 project. The kick-off meeting saw about 100 participants from ELIXIR and beyond attending. The essential vision of the CoP is to bring together DM/DS life science communities, from national (such as ELIXIR nodes) and local (research institutes, and higher education) organisations, to foster the exchange of training materials and knowledge among trainers, as well as to organise DM/DS training events.

In June 2022, a second CoP online meeting was held which helped propose a set of preliminary goals and outcomes for the CoP. In addition, the CoP’s two main meetings were used to connect with other experts and projects in the field of data management, including the ELIXIR-UK DaSH project, the German NFDI project to FAIRDOM and DataPlant.

From WP2, the project was led by ELIXIR DE, NO and UK. It was renamed to “RDM Trainer Network” and was divided into three distinct tasks:

1. Establish the RDM Trainer Network and develop a sustainability plan.

The RDM Trainer Network is essentially the community of RDM trainers that has been built up

¹⁹<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1PEAQv1Jib2Fo-5rxT19d996wb8py8Z5WMSIDVQR4bDI/edit>

²⁰<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/14q4jaiCNTz8EvjmuJybu86B0i7WWfP5amYlufkzrEPw/edit>

²¹https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1-cCx96s-FejTy5m3bwQWLI3DwiQov7ZFmv7_9ViLAHs/edit

²²https://docs.google.com/document/d/1O-FN77Q0E8ShGdzKo5_HzNaPO0RjJV061gcPr940Yh8/edit

²³https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NSEMO-n4KYB_A2dlWvUAoMIXH0BpuySg3Z90dFWnWkl/edit?pli=1#heading=h.r13pmmmidpw

in CONVERGE WP2 and this will be consolidated in the RDM Community and its implementation study, in which the Trainer Network will be a dedicated task

2. Build and organise the activities that will establish the RDM Trainer Network. A [RDM Trainer Network Meeting](#)²⁴ was organised by ELIXIR-DE, NO, UK & DINI / nestor in Berlin-Adlershof 21-22 June 2023. The event included 2 Keynotes, a Poster Session, Flash Talks, Open Tables, Social Events etc. All materials can be found [here](#)²⁵. A total of 77 participants from all over Europe attended the event. A follow up event is planned for 2024
3. Communicate and capture outcomes of the RDM Trainer Network. A RDM Trainer Network website on the ELIXIR page can be found at <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp2/rdm-trainer-network>. A Slack channel (in ELIXIR Workspace) #rdm_trainer_network was established as well as a Slack workspace created for the event Fellowship of the dat - RDM Trainer Meeting. Also a mailing list is available: rdm-trainer-network@elixir-europe.org

In summary, the RDM Trainers Network has emerged as an important outcome of this project, serving as a collaborative platform to promote knowledge sharing and skills development in Research Data Management (RDM). With a strong emphasis on outreach and dissemination, the network has promoted the importance of RDM training and practices, and facilitated the exchange of best practices in training to the wider ELIXIR RDM Community. Going forward, the activities of the RDM Trainers Network will be embedded in the ELIXIR RDM Community.

5.6.2 ELITMa

ELITMa is the ELIXIR training program in Management that evolved from the Curriculum in the same topic, developed for node coordinators in a collaboration between WP6 and WP2, whose [report version 2](#)²⁶ was revised in 2022 and can be consulted. In the ELITMa a total of eight modules is foreseen. In the WP2 uplift a [project related to ELITMa](#)²⁷ was granted, in which 3 modules of ELITMa have been developed and delivered. Module 8 *Project Management* was delivered in Spring 2023 in the frame of OATEN. On 27-29 June 2023, Module 1 (*ELIXIR Governance and Organisational Behaviour*, developed by PT, NO and ELIXIR-Hub) and Module 2 (*Module 2 Best practices from the ELIXIR portfolio of data management tools and services. A quick guide to adopting ELIXIR resources and optimising an ELIXIR Node's data management strategy*, developed by NL and ELIXIR-Hub), were [delivered in a hybrid format in Finland](#)²⁸.

²⁴<https://www.denbi.de/de-nbi-events-archiv/1522-fellowship-of-the-data-rdm-trainer-community-meeting>

²⁵<https://docs.denbi.de/s/nDjS5FnNwRi9Avj>

²⁶<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1adNkywqG2ZwU-9kJXNBcz23ZsF7y-SHK2eMxi7AofY4/edit?usp=sharing>

²⁷https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NSEMO-n4KYB_A2dIWvUAoMIXH0BpuySg3Z90dFWnWkl/edit?pli=1

²⁸https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SF2mJJSwcCiQ79_OIFx7EFoditYaMxcdxUCni6UwHec/edit

5.7 Learning Paths

Figure Caption: Learning Path for Data Stewardship

Various learning paths were created for RDM during the BioHackathon2022 as part [Project 32: Training Booster: developing FAIR training materials and learning paths²⁹](#); the [Data Management for researchers³⁰](#) learning path, [Data Stewardship³¹](#) learning path, the [Bioinforming³²](#) learning path, the [Systems Biology Community³³](#) learning path, and the [Plant Sciences Community³⁴](#) learning path. The [Learning Path protocol³⁵](#) was used to develop these learning paths, assessing its effectiveness during this project. The organisation of the hackathons was in collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform as part of the Training Platform programme 22-23 Task 2.3, co-led by ELIXIR-IT and ELIXIR-UK. The protocol is agnostic to the scientific field and is accompanied by guidelines to best support curriculum developers and trainers in designing efficient learning paths. The learning paths developed are a minimum viable product with identified and mapped topics in each respective learning path. The RDM learning paths will be further developed as part of the new ELIXIR RDM community in collaboration with the ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus Group and the ELIXIR Training Platform which will see the implementation of these learning paths in TeSS, once the functionality of Learning Paths in TeSS is available.

²⁹<https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2022/tree/main/32>

³⁰https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1sB5y8D1xTwHp2w_Hx7prABDa5UUbZxW7wVhcU8u4WHM/edit?usp=sharing

³¹<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1vnoekvXhgMldCt9UmS2agrHZO-yf6LQFD0mCsgXPwhY/edit?usp=sharing>

³²https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1qKXckAiDVyalnSSkHfxO8XW_RnMDbxfpGfpPxf3cQuo/edit?usp=drive_link

³³https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1obguy780dibFT1vJE-Q0O51c1R-4lOjIFG4fp5mulg/edit?usp=drive_link

³⁴<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/workflows/plant-phenotyping-and-plant-genomic-data-management>

³⁵<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1je6svmhFYwO5vhlkhkiW36kPmyJY65UPdL69Fxcw2w0/edit#slide=id.p>

5.8 Activities related to TeSS and RDMkit

5.8.1 TeSS & RDMkit hackathons related to training materials and events

The ultimate goal is to have all WP2 materials and trainings properly annotated in TeSS and link to the RDMkit. To kickstart this process 2 hackathons were organised, together with WP3:

1. Hackathon 1 - registering and annotating DM/DS materials in TeSS (23 September 2021, [slide deck](#) & [collaborative notes](#))
2. Hackathon 2 - Linking TeSS Resources to RDMkit (18 October 2021, [slide deck](#)³⁶ & [collaborative notes](#))

It became clear that more work needed to be done before WP2 members could annotate their training events and materials consistently. For this reason a subgroup of WP2 members set out to work towards defining a controlled vocabulary for WP2.

5.8.2 Controlled vocabularies

Together with the TeSS team and the ELIXIR Training Platform, WP2 members have been working on refining the process and terms for annotating and curating the RDM training courses and materials. From WP2 CH, DE and NO have been leading this work. During the project period, a number of meetings together with both EDAM (residing in the ELIXIR Tools Platform) and [terms4fairskills](#)³⁷ teams have taken place, including a number of “annotatethons”.

During this process, a [WP2 endorsed taglist](#)³⁸ for annotating training events & materials was finalised in 2022 for all WP2 members to use. Together with the EDAM curators the WP2 endorsed taglist was reworked and implemented in EDAM and is ready to use for TeSS. For terms4fairskills, a terminology for the skills necessary to make data FAIR and to keep it FAIR, there was already an ongoing collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform (ELIXIR Training was one of the 2 use cases in the terms4FAIRskills project (EOSC co-creation funds, [report March 2021](#)³⁹). Terms4fairskills was presented in the TeSS Club and discussions started on how to also implement this terminology in TeSS (which already has EDAM integrated in it). Currently the TeSS team is working on implementing terms4fairskills in TeSS.

In summary, the first version of a standardised RDM taglist for annotating and curating of training courses and materials was developed. This taglist was reworked, adapted and implemented in EDAM

³⁶https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1sKfDq_FbU29ySn87OUK6ipCOnYL4v9YqUWWdxMiuqU4/edit#slide=id.ged066f2eb1_0_12

³⁷<https://terms4fairskills.github.io/>

³⁸https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1QHfa6UwPmCQijlmXniNFO_bYIII38UANnnJsgBkgXrg/edit#gid=0

³⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705219>

and is ready to use for TeSS and Terms4fairskills. Regular updates and curation are needed to further improve the taglist.

5.8.3 RDMkit: Links to TeSS and Your Role Pages

WP2 members have been collaborating with WP3 (more specifically Task 3.4) to make sure links from RDMkit to trainings in TeSS were established. Details about the implementation are given in [D3.4](#)⁴⁰ (Section 4.6.2).

During various WP3 hackathons, ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 has provided the content for the [Your Role pages in RDMkit](#)⁴¹, based on the [NPOS/ELIXIR data steward competency framework](#)⁴² (incorporated in the [EBI competency Hub](#)⁴³ as well). These Your Role pages are currently under revision as a result of the recent WP3 Ghent contentathon and new roles are being added.

Data Steward: infrastructure Data Steward with focus on tools (software) and IT infrastructure for data management. Related pages ▾	Data Steward: policy Data Steward with focus on data policies. Related pages ▾
Data Steward: research Data Steward with focus on management of research data. Related pages ▾	Researcher Researchers generating and reusing data. Related pages ▾

5.9 Collaboration with ELIXIR Training Platform

The work in WP2 has been performed in close collaboration with and building on the assets and guidelines of the ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP), see also Figure below. Examples of collaborations and contributions:

- WP2 members are contributing to the [FAIR Handbook for FAIR training materials](#)⁴⁴
- WP2 members have contributed to the Learning Paths work (see also above under 5.7)

⁴⁰<https://zenodo.org/record/7858238#.ZEZW6-zML0o>

⁴¹https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/your_role

⁴²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3471707>

⁴³<https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>

⁴⁴<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-training-handbook/>

- [ELIXIR Training Lesson Template](#)⁴⁵: The requirement to have a centralised lesson template when developing training materials collaboratively (for example, with members from different ELIXIR Nodes) was evident in ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2. Previously, in other ELIXIR projects, these materials were developed either using templates from specific Institutes (which did not reflect the collaborative nature of the authors and collaborators of the respective lessons), via Google documents or other media that was not FAIR, reducing the visibility of its output. WP2 started discussions with the ELIXIR Training Platform and established a first prototype of the ELIXIR Training Lesson Template, which allowed for the development of training lessons collaboratively with members from different ELIXIR Nodes in a FAIR way. The first version of this template was published [here](#)⁴⁶. This work will be further developed in the new ELIXIR Training Programme 24-28.
- The CONVERGE tag is now added to the ELIXIR [Training Metrics Database](#)⁴⁷ (TMD) so CONVERGE funded training events can be annotated and identified.
- At the AHM 2021 a TrP-WP6-WP2 workshop was organised: [Embedding the Coordinators' Triangle \(TeC-TrC-NC\) in the operations of ELIXIR Nodes](#)⁴⁸
- Collaboration of WP2 with WP7 will continue in the future in the context of Federated EGA and the ELIXIR Federated Human Data community according to their needs in a co-production model with the ELIXIR Training Platform.

⁴⁵<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-LessonTemplate-MkDocs/>

⁴⁶<https://zenodo.org/record/7913092>

⁴⁷<https://training-metrics-dev.elixir-europe.org/>

⁴⁸<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AmQZtmtKXHWXh6UA7gZ4mbmkXp5R3vIw8ZUnASwWbAo/edit#heading=h.gdgxs>

6. Conclusions

During the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project period, RDM professionals, training experts and trainers from ELIXIR and beyond identified gaps in the Nodes' RDM training programmes and defined priority topics (DMP, Data Stewardship, FAIR/metadata and Reproducibility) for training development. Collaborative work from all the ELIXIR Nodes during ELIXIR-CONVERGE resulted in an extensive ELIXIR Data Management/Data Stewardship (DM/DS) course portfolio which aligns with the Nodes' RDM training strategies. In total, materials belonging to 133 training events, which were organised by 18 Nodes and served 4226 participants, were developed.

The ELIXIR DM/DS portfolio includes both generic DM/DS resources and materials, as well as specific materials related to the priority topics mentioned above, and it also includes training materials for specific domains (e.g. the Plant Demonstrator). The course portfolio is available in [TeSS](#)⁴⁹, in which training materials are tagged with RDM terms to increase their findability, and links to relevant training materials were included in [RDMkit](#)⁵⁰. In collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform, the learning paths methodology has been applied to RDM for data stewards and researchers (e.g. with the Plants Sciences and the System Biology Communities), and work is ongoing to extend the [ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer programme](#)⁵¹ to tackle the challenges that exist in teaching RDM. Moreover, during ELIXIR-CONVERGE, a strong RDM trainers network was formed, establishing solid RDM training expertise within the Nodes. This emerging network raised great interest in the Nodes, showing their willingness to work together on developing training materials, sharing their knowledge, and establishing best practices and standards for RDM training.

In 2023, the ELIXIR RDM Community was initiated, and the network of RDM trainers will be an integral part of this Community. This will continue to enable the upskilling of RDM trainers and scaling up RDM training capacity in the Nodes, while bridging to RDM professionals within the Nodes and outside ELIXIR as well.

7. Impact

During the CONVERGE project period, all the Nodes that are members of WP2 have unlocked and increased their RDM expertise and their RDM training expertise and together worked on the common goals of WP2. Collaborators from other CONVERGE Work Packages and from other institutes and organisations in the Nodes have also been involved in the activities. This means that the reach of the WP2 outputs is huge, more than 4000 people have actively been trained in one of the

⁴⁹<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵⁰<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵¹<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/training/train-the-trainer>

training events. For almost all the WP2 activities routes to sustainability have been identified, either in the context of the ELIXIR Training Platform or in the ELIXIR RDM Community. This means that we have secured the outcomes of WP2 and will be able to build on them going forward.

8. Next Steps

In the last year of the project, attention has been given to identify the next steps towards sustainability and embedding for a number of the specific WP2 activities and outcomes. This was discussed during the WP1/WP2 meeting in March 2023 in Prague and during the CONVERGE Long-term Sustainability Meeting in June 2023 in Dublin. Many of the next steps will take place in the context of the ELIXIR Training Platform Programme 2024-2028 and/or in the ELIXIR RDM Community.

Some examples, some of which are already mentioned in Section 5, are:

- increasing findability and reusability of the developed courses and modules by optimising annotation and linking in TeSS, RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook
- encouraging (re)use of the RDM materials in ELIXIR Nodes
- increasing RDM training capacity in Nodes by finalising and launching the RDM Train the Trainer programme
- gathering the RDM courses in the portfolio into learning paths for specific audiences, thus shaping the ELIXIR RDM curriculum
- follow-up work related to ELITMa will be done in the context of the ELIXIR-STEERS project that has just been granted

Through the collaborative efforts within the ELIXIR RDM Community, we aim to advance the field of research data management, empower individuals with essential skills, and ensure the widespread adoption of best practices across the research community.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

